

IDENTIFICATION OF CARDIogenic SHOCK IN EMERGENCY TRIAGE NURSING

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Background

- CGS is a complex, multifactorial syndrome resulting from myocardial pump failure and low cardiac output
- Life-threatening with mortality rate >50%
- Multisystem organ failure due to inadequate perfusion
- High cost of care estimated \$69.7 billion by 2023
- Emergent nature of CGS requires differentiation from other shock etiologies to provide targeted treatment

Problem

- Lack of a standardized process for early identification and differentiation of CGS leading to a delay in the initiation of targeted treatment, increasing mortality risk

Purpose

- Address the need for consistent, timely, and accurate differentiation of CGS
- Provide an algorithm to assist frontline nursing staff to quickly recognize and triage patients according to their needs

Framework: Iowa Model

- Developed in the 1990s
- Facilitates translation & implementation of research into EBP
- Lens through which the project is interpreted

Method

- Design: Quality Improvement
- Protocol with criteria for identification of CGS and process steps
- Setting: Non-profit community hospital, Orange County, CA
- Sample: All adult patients presenting with symptoms of shock or shock diagnosis

Algorithm

Recommendations

- The use of an algorithm standardizes patient care and directs the triage nurse
- Pre-implementation education provides the rationale for use, details on shock etiology, classification, and how to place nurse-initiated orders
- After a successful pilot, the algorithm becomes the standard workflow

Limitations

- The pilot took place in one department, limiting the nurses trained
- Potential bias due to initial evaluation provided by nurse educator and manager
- Lack of evaluation from the triage nurses, which would have provided a working understanding of the feasibility of implementation

Conclusion

- Differentiation of CGS is necessary to initiate targeted treatment
- Nurse-initiated orders save time & provide the necessary information to differentiate CGS
- Prompt recognition by the emergency triage nurse begins the care pathway
- Classification dictates the urgency of patient needs
- CGS is life-threatening & requires urgent triage and treatment
- Algorithm standardizes care leading to improved outcomes

References

